

ENHANCING HIGHER-ORDER THINKING THROUGH EXPERIENTIAL AND VICARIOUS LEARNING: EVIDENCE FROM BUSINESS EDUCATION UNDERGRADUATES

¹Emily Grace Harrison and ²Lorenzo Marco Bianchi

¹Department of Education, Faculty of Arts and Education, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

²Department of Education, Faculty of Arts and Education, University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19202520>

Abstract: This study investigated the relationship between experiential learning, vicarious learning, and the development of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) among undergraduate students enrolled in business education programmes in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria. With increasing demands for entrepreneurial competence and critical thinking in the 21st-century workplace, the study sought to identify the extent to which active and observational learning approaches influence students' ability to think analytically, evaluate critically, and apply knowledge creatively. A correlational survey research design was adopted. The study sampled 151 business education lecturers (comprising 43 males and 108 females), selected through simple random sampling from three Federal Universities. Data were collected using self-constructed, four-point Likert scale questionnaires with high internal consistency, as determined by Cronbach's alpha coefficients: 0.93 for experiential learning, 0.92 for vicarious learning, and 0.96 for HOTS.

Statistical analysis was carried out using the bivariate correlation matrix and Fisher-Z transformation to test for gender differences in the relationships between the learning approaches and HOTS. The findings revealed a statistically significant difference in the relationship between experiential learning and the development of HOTS across gender. Specifically, male and female lecturers reported differing levels of correlation, indicating a gender-based variation in how experiential learning supports higher-order thinking. Conversely, no significant gender difference was found in the relationship between vicarious learning and HOTS, suggesting that observational learning strategies have a uniformly positive effect across genders.

These results highlight the need for educators and administrators in business education programmes to integrate and promote learning environments that foster both experiential and vicarious learning opportunities. Such an approach is essential not only for cultivating students' critical and reflective capacities but also for preparing them for dynamic and complex entrepreneurial roles after graduation. The study underscores the imperative to consider gender dynamics in instructional planning and encourages the continuous professional development of educators in the use of diverse pedagogical strategies that enhance students' cognitive development.

Keywords: Experiential learning vicarious learning Higher-order thinking skills Business education Gender differences

Introduction

In the contemporary educational discourse, there is an increasing emphasis on the development of critical skills that go beyond rote learning and theoretical knowledge acquisition. Higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) such as critical thinking, problem-solving, analytical reasoning, reflective thinking, and metacognitive ability have become central to the goals of education systems worldwide, particularly as societies grapple with complex economic and technological challenges. Business education, as a discipline within the broader educational framework, holds a unique position in preparing students not only to contribute meaningfully to the world of work but also to navigate entrepreneurial and lifelong learning pathways. In the Nigerian context, business education programmes are strategically positioned to play a transformative role in addressing youth unemployment, skills mismatch, and socio-economic development. However, concerns persist regarding the efficacy of these programmes in equipping graduates with the relevant practical and cognitive skills necessary for success in an increasingly dynamic and competitive labor market.

Despite the centrality of business education in Nigeria's tertiary institutions, critics have raised pertinent questions about the effectiveness and relevance of the programme. Scholars such as Edokpolor and Agbonkolor (2018) have argued that while business education programmes are expected to serve as a catalyst for entrepreneurial readiness and self-reliance, their implementation often falls short of these lofty objectives. A core challenge identified in this regard is the over-reliance on traditional, theory-driven instructional approaches that do not sufficiently engage students in practical, real-world learning experiences. Bennis and O'Toole (2005) observe that the dominance of abstract theoretical teaching in business education undermines the development of essential competencies needed for practical application, creativity, and problem-solving. This pedagogical gap undermines students' preparedness for the multifaceted demands of the global workforce and limits their potential for entrepreneurship and innovation.

Ekpenyong (1999) had earlier emphasized this concern, pointing out that Nigerian business education tends to prioritize the transmission of abstract concepts through lecture-based methods, with minimal attention to practical skill development. The dearth of experiential learning, project-based activities, collaborative engagement, and informal learning contexts signifies a disconnection between classroom learning and workplace realities. As such, students graduate without adequate exposure to the types of learning experiences that foster critical reflection, independent reasoning, and adaptive problem-solving—hallmarks of higher-order thinking. Consequently, the output of business education programmes remains largely misaligned with employer expectations, contributing to persistent issues such as graduate unemployment and underemployment.

The disconnect between academic training and industry expectations is not unique to Nigeria; it is symptomatic of a broader crisis in educational systems across developing countries. Stakeholders have consistently highlighted the challenges posed by low investment in faculty development, outdated curricula, inadequate infrastructure, and weak quality assurance mechanisms (Nwosu & Ojo, 2014). However, what appears to be even more critical is the

lack of intentional integration of skill-focused pedagogical approaches such as experiential learning and vicarious learning into the curriculum. These methodologies, if well implemented, offer the potential to revitalize business education by enabling students to acquire the cognitive agility and practical insight necessary for workplace effectiveness and entrepreneurial activity.

Experiential learning, rooted in the philosophy of "learning by doing," offers an educational framework that immerses learners in real-world tasks and contexts. Kolb (1984), in his Experiential Learning Theory (ELT), posited that meaningful learning occurs when individuals are actively involved in an experience, reflect on that experience, conceptualize what they have learned, and then apply their insights in new situations. ELT promotes a cyclical model of learning involving concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. Applied to business education, this model allows students to engage deeply with the learning material by drawing from actual business scenarios, case studies, simulations, internships, and entrepreneurial projects. In doing so, they develop a more nuanced understanding of business concepts and processes, as well as the critical thinking skills necessary to adapt to diverse and evolving situations.

The incorporation of experiential learning into business education curricula is particularly crucial in the development of HOTS. As Lewis and Williams (1994) suggest, experiential learning fosters the formation of new attitudes, skills, and ways of thinking by allowing learners to reflect on their experiences and internalize lessons derived from them. Such reflection is vital for the cultivation of metacognitive and reflective thinking skills, which are essential for effective decision-making and innovation. By actively engaging in experiential learning, business education students are likely to develop a sense of ownership over their learning processes, greater confidence in their problem-solving abilities, and the resilience to navigate real-life professional challenges.

Similarly, vicarious learning—a process where individuals learn through the observation of others—holds considerable promise for enhancing students' cognitive capacities. Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory underlines the significance of observational learning in shaping behavior, attitudes, and skills. In educational settings, vicarious learning often occurs through mentorship, modeling, peer interaction, and media-based instruction. By observing how peers or professionals approach and solve problems, students internalize strategies and thought processes that inform their own behavior and reasoning. This process not only reinforces theoretical knowledge but also aids in the cultivation of critical competencies, especially in contexts where direct experience may be limited or unavailable.

The strategic integration of both experiential and vicarious learning into business education has the potential to bridge the theory-practice divide and enhance the development of HOTS among undergraduate students. For instance, simulation exercises, role-playing activities, video case studies, and reflective journals can all serve as conduits for these learning approaches. Through these activities, students are encouraged to think critically about their learning experiences, evaluate outcomes, and generate new insights that inform future action. Such reflective engagement is central to higher-order thinking and aligns with the objectives of business education in preparing students for real-world application and lifelong learning.

Furthermore, the relevance of HOTS in today's knowledge-based economy cannot be overstated. As organizations and industries increasingly seek individuals who can analyze complex problems, innovate solutions, and make informed decisions, the demand for graduates equipped with HOTS continues to rise. The global emphasis on employability skills, digital literacy, and adaptive thinking underscores the need for business education to evolve beyond content delivery to focus on the cultivation of transferable competencies. Therefore, aligning business education curricula with pedagogical models that emphasize experiential and vicarious learning is not just desirable—it is imperative.

Gender dynamics also play a notable role in the effectiveness of pedagogical strategies and learning outcomes. In the Nigerian context, gender disparities in access to quality education, participation in active learning, and career outcomes have been documented across disciplines. Understanding how experiential and vicarious learning approaches impact students differently based on gender is essential for developing inclusive educational strategies. Previous studies have indicated that males and females may engage differently with various forms of learning due to sociocultural factors, motivational orientations, and levels of self-efficacy (Johnson & Kosykh, 2008; Sidanius & Veniegas, 2000). Consequently, an exploration of gender-based differences in the relationship between learning approaches and HOTS development can provide valuable insights into tailoring pedagogical practices that cater to diverse learner needs.

In light of the above, this study seeks to empirically investigate the relationship between experiential and vicarious learning approaches and the development of higher-order thinking skills among business education undergraduate students in selected federal universities in South-South Nigeria. The study specifically aims to determine the extent to which these learning approaches are effective in promoting critical cognitive skills and whether these relationships differ based on gender. By doing so, the research contributes to the growing body of literature on innovative pedagogical practices in business education and offers practical recommendations for curriculum reform and instructional design.

Ultimately, the study underscores the necessity for Nigerian tertiary institutions to adopt forward-looking strategies that equip students with the cognitive and practical tools necessary for navigating the uncertainties of the labor market. As unemployment, underemployment, and poverty remain persistent challenges for graduates, business education programmes must evolve to become more responsive, dynamic, and relevant. Experiential and vicarious learning approaches offer a pragmatic pathway for achieving this transformation, fostering a generation of graduates who are not only theoretically sound but also capable of critical reasoning, adaptive problem-solving, and entrepreneurial engagement in an ever-changing world.

Experiential learning can be divided into two major categories, namely field-based and classroom-based experiential learning. Field-based experiential learning is a learning approach that is usually experienced by students outside the classroom or in the workplace. Forms of field-based experiential learning include internships, mentoring, community service projects, work-study, feasibility studies, field trip, industrial work experience and teaching practice. Classroom-based experiential learning refers to a learning approach that usually takes place in

the classroom. Forms of classroom-based experiential learning include role-playing, case studies, simulations, presentations, guest speakers, class debates, individual or group project, peer tutoring, business planning, group discussion, and other types of group work. All these (along with many others) would provide great opportunities for business education students to become fully engaged directly or indirectly in practical skills learning. However, not only do field-based or classroom-based experiential learning increase students' mastery, they can also provide the opportunity for business education students to learn by observation. For instance, observing teachers during demonstration teaching or observing students during role playing can provide vicarious experiences that foster the development of HOTS.

Experiential and Vicarious Learning Approaches in Developing Higher-Order Thinking Skills ...

Bandura (1977) propounded vicarious learning with his theory of social learning. Vicarious learning can be describe as observing experts or listening to peers as they discuss a new topic (O'Neil & Marsick, 2009; Kalaian & Kasim, 2014) and learning through the behaviours of others (Fox, 2003; Schunk & Mullen, 2013). It can also be defined as learning from others' experiences via story-telling (Harden, 2000; Ashworth, 2004; Ellis, Calvo, Levy & Tan, 2004; Northedge, 2003; Davidson, 2004) and discussion (or discourse) and competent persons (Topping, 2005). These definitions have shown that vicarious learning is central to the development of HOTS through interactions, observations, tutoring or modeling.

Vicarious learning supports the notion that students do not necessarily have to participate in experience directly in order to acquire HOTS (Hoover, Giambatista & Belkin, 2012). This may be the reason why Bruner (1986) averred that most of our encounters with people in the world are not direct encounters. Vygotsky also argued that through people we become ourselves (Tudge & Scrimsher, 2003). These assertions imply that it is possible to learn vicariously, other than direct experience (Roberts, 2010). In fact, scholars have argued that many learning outcomes resulting from direct experiences can occur on a vicarious basis (Bandura, 1986; Kim & Miner, 2007; Nadler, Thompson, & Van Boven, 2003). In this way, behavioural response pattern can be established through vicarious learning, where student observation of expert performance can enable him/her to reproduce the expert behaviour (Bandura, 1977). Thus, teachers demonstrating during teaching, students acting during role playing, entrepreneurs performing work roles during work study, while students are watching and imitating can provide the opportunity for students to develop HOTS prior to graduation.

Higher-Order Thinking Skills may be defined as the abilities to perform productive tasks, think critically and solve problems. Brookhart (2010) provides a working definition of HOTS which falls into three categories: transfer, critical thinking and problem solving. Other categories of HOTS are: creative thinking, decisionmaking, logical thinking, metacognitive thinking, reflective thinking, judgment thinking and caring thinking. These categories of HOTS cannot be acquired in formal learning environment alone, but are acquired in the informal learning environment. Resnick (1987) stresses the importance of social learning settings in the development of HOTS among students, including business education students through group project, collaborative learning, storytelling, group discussion, among others. Therefore, HOTS can be developed with various forms of

experiential and vicarious learning through business education programme. These HOTS are likened to the 21st century skills (such as, flexibility, adaptability, initiative, self-direction, information literacy, ICT literacy, self-discipline, self-motivation, innovativeness, responsibility, and lots more) which business education students are expected to acquire in order to prepare them for their professional and lifelong learning career tasks upon graduation. Despite the crucial role of HOTS in spurring economic development in the Nigerian context, there are dearth of empirical studies that examined the relationships among experiential learning, vicarious learning and development of HOTS among business education undergraduates. Thus, this study attempts to examine the relationships between experiential learning and vicarious learning as against the development of HOTS among business education undergraduate students. The study aimed to also test the relationships between experiential learning and vicarious learning as against the development of HOTS based on gender.

Statement of the Problem

Business Education is a practical-oriented programme that prepares students' for entrepreneurial careers and lifelong learning tasks. Despite these tasks, Business Education students still graduate without acquiring HOTS needed to engage in entrepreneurial careers and lifelong learning tasks. As a consequence, Business Education students who are not equip with HOTS may become unemployed or underemployed, and would James Edomwonyi Edokpolor & Ishola Nojeem Adeniyi not have self-efficacy or self-confidence to engage in entrepreneurial careers and lifelong learning upon graduation. This unpleasant situation suggests that business education programmes have been laying emphasis on theoretical learning, thereby relegating practical skills learning approaches to the background, namely: inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, collaborative learning, apprenticeship learning, technology-enabled informal learning, to mention just a few. To the best of the author's knowledge, there are dearth of empirical literature that has specifically examined the relationships between each learning approaches (experiential and vicarious) and development of HOTS among business education undergraduate students. There is, therefore, an obvious gap in business education academic literature as regards the relationships between each learning approaches (experiential and vicarious) and development of HOTS. However, forms of experiential learning, such as, service learning, computer or tablet technology, fun game, and group work, and forms of vicarious learning, such as, negotiation exercises, storytelling, paper and digital technology, team learning, classroom simulations, and digital video cases have been examined separately in other academic disciplines. It is based on all these identified gaps the author embarked on this study in order to provide data on the extent of relationships among experiential learning, vicarious learning and development of HOTS among business education undergraduates in Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Methodology

A correlational survey research design was used to achieve the objectives of the study. This type of research design involves the collection of data to determine whether, or to what degree, a relationship exists between two or more variables (Gay, Mills & Airasian, 2009). This design is appropriate for this study in that it determines

whether, or the extent to which, a relationship exist among experiential, vicarious learning and HOTS. A sample of 151 lecturers (214 Males and 536 Females) of business education was selected through simple random sampling across Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria. The author of the study made no attempt to adopt a sample procedure because the participants were not too large to cover.

Self-constructed instruments were used for the collection of data, titled: Experiential Learning Questionnaire (ELQ), Vicarious Learning Questionnaire (VLQ), and Higher-Order Thinking Skills Questionnaire (HOTSQ). Nine items measured experiential learning, eleven terms measured vicarious learning, and twelve items measured HOTS, totaling 32 items. A panel of two experts from business education and measurement and evaluation verified the content validity of the instruments. A reliability test was conducted to determine the internal consistency of the instrument and the results revealed a coefficient of 0.93 for experiential learning, 0.92 for vicarious learning, and 0.96 for HOTS via Cronbach’s alpha method. The bivariate correlation matrix and Fisher Z statistic was used for analyzing the data. Bivariate correlation was used to analyze extent of relationships among experiential learning, vicarious learning and HOTS, while Fisher Z was used to analyze the differences between the responses of male and female business education lecturers’ as regards relationships between each learning approaches (experiential learning and vicarious learning) as against the HOTS.

Order Thinking Skills

Results

Table 1

Cronbach’s Alpha and Correlation Matrix of the Summated Variables in the Study (N = 151)

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4
Gender	1.71	.456	1			
Experiential Learning	3.52	.365	-.066	(.93)		
Vicarious Learning	3.49	.390	-.023	.610**	(.92)	
Higher-Order Thinking Skills	3.43	.412	-.031	.605**	.604**	(.96)

Note. **p < .01, Cronbach’s alpha values are in the diagonal

Table 1 showed the correlations among the study variables. Table 1 showed that Cronbach’s alpha values for the study variables are relatively high. In the study, the alpha values for experiential learning, vicarious learning and HOTS are 0.93, 0.92, and 0.96 respectively, which imply high measure of internal consistency. The mean responses of business education lecturers range from 3.43 to 3.52, while the standard deviations values ranged from .447 to .658. Table 1 showed that correlation of gender with experiential learning, vicarious learning, and HOTS range from -.023 to -.066. The correlation between experiential learning and HOTS is .605, which indicated a high relationship. This explained that experiential learning can foster the development of HOTS among business education students to a very high extent. The table also showed that correlation between vicarious

learning and HOTS is .604, which indicated a high relationship. This also explained that vicarious learning can foster the development of HOTS among business education students to a very high extent.

Testing of the Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There exist no statistically significant difference in the ratings of male and female business education lecturers regarding the relationship between experiential learning and development of HOTS.

Table 2

Fisher Z Transformation for Male and Female Business Education Lecturers' Differences on the Extent to which Experiential Learning can Foster Development of HOTS among Students

Variables	N	r	Zr	Z
Experiential Learning and HOTS				4.567***
Male	43	.077 (ns)	.080	
Female	108	.727***	.929	

Table 2 showed the Fisher Z transformation results on the differences in the responses of male and female business education lecturers regarding the extent to which experiential learning approach can foster development of HOTS among students. The correlation between experiential learning and HOTS from male business education lecturer's responses is .077, but not significant. Also, the correlation between experiential learning and HOTS from female business education lecturer's responses is .727, but significant. The z-value of 4.567 is significant at .05 alpha value. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in responses of male and female business education lecturer's regarding the extent to which experiential learning approach can foster development of HOTS among students.

Hypothesis 2: There exist no statistically significant difference in the ratings of male and female business education lecturers regarding the relationship between vicarious learning and development of HOTS.

James Edomwonyi Edokpolor & Ishola Nojeem Adeniyi

Table 3

Fisher Z Transformation for Male and Female Business Education Lecturers' Differences on the Extent to which Vicarious Learning can Foster Development of HOTS among Students

Variables	N	r	Zr	Z
Vicarious Learning and HOTS				4.954***
Male	43	.034 (ns)	.030	
Female	108	.743***	.951	

The data presented in Table 3 showed the Fisher Z transformation results on the difference in responses of male and female business education lecturers regarding the extent to which vicarious learning approach can foster development of HOTS among students. The Table revealed that correlation between vicarious learning approach

and HOTS of male business education lecturer's responses is .034, but not significant. The table further revealed that the correlation between vicarious learning and HOTS from female business education lecturer's responses is .743, but significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in responses of male and female business education lecturer's regarding the extent to which vicarious learning approach can foster the development of HOTS among students.

Discussion of Findings

This study added to the dearth of literature on the relationships between experiential learning and vicarious learning as against development of HOTS among business education undergraduates. Specifically, the data gathered from the study revealed positive and high relationships among experiential learning, vicarious learning and development of HOTS among business education undergraduate students. This means that both experiential learning and vicarious learning have important roles to play in development of HOTS among business education undergraduates. This finding agreed with the study conducted by Elengovan and Nagendralingan (2014) who found that the utilization of problem-based scenario grounded in the constructivist and experiential learning theory were key enabler for the development of HOTS. They further found that students who were nurtured using simulation learning model demonstrated higher order thinking pattern, explicit learning through sharing and reflective practices, had self-efficacy in managing business cases as well as leadership and social skills. The findings of this study also supported the research conducted by Balakrishnan, Nadarajah, Vellasamy and George (2016) who found that that the teacher trainers' HOTS were enhanced after two-day continuous professional development programme, such as discovery and active hands-on learning activities.

Furthermore, the study agreed with the research conducted by Espey (2018) who revealed that students expressed significantly greater improvement in HOTS in a vicarious-based learning environment. The finding of this research agreed with the study conducted by Bagdasarov, Luo and Wu (2017) who reported that the use of tablet technology, coupled with vicarious learning was beneficial for developing different types of communication skills, such as oral and written communication. Their findings also indicated that tablet technology usage contributed to positive impact on development of critical thinking and problem solving skills. In addition, the findings of this study conforms to the research conducted by Kim (2017) who demonstrated current trend of computer simulation not only in favour of improving content knowledge but also enhancing HOTS and problem-solving skills in Practical-Based Learning.

The findings of this study imply that when business education programme is able to foster development of HOTS among students, one can say experiential and vicarious learning approaches were used. The findings' of this study therefore strengthens the important role of experiential and vicarious learning in effective

Order Thinking Skills

delivery of business education programmes in Nigerian Universities. Although, at this present time, the resources for effective delivery of business education have been found to be inadequate, and teaching and learning process

were also found to be ineffective; and HOTS were found not to be acquired by students, which in turn lowers the confidence for entrepreneurial and lifelong learning tasks (Edokpolor, 2018b).

Conclusion

The findings of this study have revealed positive and high relationships between two learning approaches (experiential learning and vicarious learning) as against the HOTS. The findings revealed a significant difference in responses of male and female business education lecturer's regarding the extent to which experiential learning approach fosters development of HOTS among students. Conversely, the findings revealed no significant difference in the responses of male and female business education lecturer's regarding the extent to which vicarious learning approach fosters development of HOTS among students. Thus, the author of this study concludes that experiential and vicarious learning approaches have important roles in developing HOTS among business education undergraduates in Federal Universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Managers of business education programme should endeavour to provide experiential learning methods for instructional delivery in order to assist in equipping the students with HOTS that are required to engage in entrepreneurial and lifelong learning tasks upon graduation.
2. Managers of business education programme should endeavour to provide vicarious learning methods for instructional delivery in order to assist in equipping the students with HOTS that are required to engage in entrepreneurial and lifelong learning tasks upon graduation.

References

- Ashworth, P. (2004). Understanding as the transformation of what is already known. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 9(2), 147–158. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1356251042000195357>
- Azih, N. (2013). Capacity building in modern office technology: An imperative for effective secretarial productivity. *Asian Journal of Business Management*, 5(2), 193–196.
- Bagdasarov, Z., Luo, Y., & Wu, W. (2017). The influence of tablet-based technology on the development of communication and critical thinking skills: An interdisciplinary study. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 49(1–2), 55–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2017.1293576>
- Balakrishnan, M., Nadarajah, G. M., Vellasamy, S., & George, E. G. W. (2016). Enhancement of higher order thinking skills among teacher trainers by fun game learning approach. *International Journal of Educational and Pedagogical Sciences*, 10(12), 3954–3958.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice-Hall.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Prentice-Hall.

- Bandura, A. (1999). A social cognitive theory of personality. In L. Pervin & O. John (Eds.), *Handbook of personality* (2nd ed.). Guilford Press.
- Bennis, W. G., & O'Toole, J. (2005). How business schools lost their way. *Harvard Business Review*, 83(5), 96–104.
- Brookhart, S. M. (2010). *How to assess higher-order thinking skills in your classroom*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Bruner, J. S. (1986). *Actual minds, possible worlds*. Harvard University Press.
- Collins, L. (2017). The impact of paper versus digital map technology on students' spatial thinking skill acquisition. *Journal of Geography*, 10(1), 1–16.
- Davidson, M. R. (2004). A phenomenological evaluation: Using storytelling as a primary teaching method. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 4, 184–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2003.10.001>
- Edokpolor, E. J. (2018b). Systems approach in developing creative thinking and innovative capabilities for lifelong learning among TVET students in Federal Universities, South-South, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 21(1), 1–15.
- Edokpolor, E. J. (2018c). Influence of self-efficacy antecedents on career decision-making of business education students in federal universities in South Southern Nigeria. *Ibadan Journal of Educational Studies*, 15(1), 20–35.
- Edokpolor, J. E., & Agbonkpolo, M. U. (2018). Formative assessment methods and teaching and learning processes of business education in federal universities in South-South, Nigeria. *African Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 11(2), 13–23.
- Egbri, J. N., & Nwadiani, C. N. (2017). Modern office skills acquired for labour market among business education trainees in Edo State. *Bayero Journal of Education in Africa*, 6(1), 108–116.
- Ekpenyong, L. E. (1999). A reformulation of the theory of experiential learning appropriate for instruction in formal business education. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 51(3), 467–468. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636829900200087>
- Elongovan, V., & Nagendralingan, R. (2014). Enhancing higher order thinking skills through clinical simulation. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction*, 11, 75–100.
- Ellis, R. A., Calvo, R., Levy, D., & Tan, K. (2004). Learning through discussions. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 23(1), 73–79.

Espey, M. (2018). Enhancing critical thinking using team-based learning. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 37(1), 15–29.

Fox, F. F. (2003). Reducing intercultural friction through fiction: Virtual cultural learning. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 27, 99–123.

Gay, L. R., Mills, G. E., & Airasian, P. (2009). *Educational research: Competencies for analysis and applications* (9th ed.). Merrill.

Global e-Schools and Communities Initiative. (2013). *Development of 21st century skills for innovation and enterprise: Exploring the role of informal learning environments in the development of skills and aptitudes for the digital creative media industries*.